

LIFE SATISFACTION OF HIGHER SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract:

Teachers role is numerous and utterly important. A teacher's contribution in an individual's life is long lasting. Job satisfaction always increases the capability, productivity of the employee, which is beneficiary for the institution also. If a teacher is satisfied with his job, he can contribute to the development of the students. The present study aims to signify the level of life satisfaction among higher secondary school teachers and to find significant difference in life satisfaction with regard to gender, locality of school, type of management, medium of instruction and teaching stream. Findings of the study revealed average level of life satisfaction among higher secondary school teachers and there is no significant towards gender, locality of school, type of management, medium of instruction and teaching stream towards life satisfaction of higher secondary school teachers.

Introduction:

Teaching is one of the noble professions in the world. Almost all the educational commissions and committees have focused on the teacher's role and duties, as well as their working conditions. Teachers are the spine of the society. His role is numerous and utterly important. A teacher's contribution in an individual's life is long lasting. The Education Commission (1964-66) or The Kothari Commission properly said that of all the different factor which influence the quality of education and its contribution to the national development, the quality competence and character of teachers are undoubtedly the most significant. Nothing is more important than securing a sufficient supply of high quality recruits to the teaching profession providing them with the best of work in which they can be fully effective" (Kumar, P. 2014). The Programme of Action (1992) has put forward some guidelines regarding teacher recruitment, job benefits, etc. it stated that, the status of teachers has had a direct bearing on the quality of education, and many of the ills of the latter can be ascribed to the indifferent manner in which society has looked upon the teacher and the manner in which many teachers have performed their functions (source: <http://www.teindia.nic.in/Files/Reports/CCR/POA>).

Traditionally teachers enjoyed a higher status in the society and they also enjoyed great respect. But in the last few decades, teacher's position has diminished due to various factors. The teachers in India suffer from neglect, poverty, indifference, insecurity and obviously disrespect.

The concept of life-satisfaction denotes an *overall* evaluation of life. So the appraisal that life is exciting does not necessarily mean that it is satisfying. There may be too much excitement in life, and too few other qualities. An overall evaluation of life involves all relevant criteria in the mind of the individual: for example, how good one feels, how well expectations are likely to be met and how desirable various factors are deemed to be, etc. The object of evaluation is life-as-a-whole; not a specific area of life, e.g., employment. Enjoyment of work may add to the appreciation of life, but does not constitute it. This book considers four kinds of satisfaction; (1) global life-satisfaction (GLS), (2) satisfaction with housing (SH), (3) satisfaction with finances (SF) and (4) satisfaction with social contacts (SC).

Life satisfaction has been measured in relation to economic standing, amount of education, experiences, and the people's residence as well as many other topics. Seligman, a professor of psychology at the University of Pennsylvania, uses a formula for happiness that encompasses the factors that go into general happiness. The formula is $H = S + C + V$. In this formula H stands for a person's enduring level of happiness, S is the set range (or biological boundaries), C is the circumstances of a person's life, and V are the factors under a person's voluntary control.

According to Wolman (1973), it is the attainment of a desired end and fulfillment of an essential condition. Lavinga (1979), a teacher who is happy with his work and finds satisfaction of his life, plays a pivotal role in the upliftment of society. Verma and Suri (1981) are of the view that frustration should not creep in teacher's life as it may directly influence students and the teacher himself. Life satisfaction is a broader term which includes satisfaction in relation to job and to the basic general requirements of life (Singh and Mulay, 1982). Brown (1985) in the Dictionary of Life considers it to be a dynamic process which goes on throughout one's life.

Need of the Study:

Teaching profession is one of the most challenging one. It is the responsibility of the teacher to develop his students so that they can become individually, socially useful. Not only the academic responsibilities, but teachers have to shoulder many administrative duties in the institution. Compared to other professions, teachers

are underpaid in India. If they are to perform their strenuous duty effectively their working conditions should be made satisfactory.

Method and Sampling Frame:

Considering the objectives of the study the investigator had adopted survey method. The present study concerned with the higher secondary school teachers. The teachers from government, government aided and private schools were taken to constitute the population for the present study. The simple random sampling technique is adopted in the present study. The size of the sample is 300. A personal data sheet was also prepared by the investigator to know about the higher secondary school teacher’s gender, locality of school, type of management, medium of instruction and teaching stream.

Tool:

Samples were collected using a personal data sheet prepared by the researcher. Life Satisfaction Scale by Neugarten (1961) was used for measuring life satisfaction. Items are rated on a three-point rating scale ranging from “agree”, “Disagree” and “?”. “Agree” and “disagree” are given 2 points and “?” scored as 1 point. Maximum scores on this scale are 40 and minimum score is 20. The higher scores has the greater degree of life satisfaction. The investigator has calculated the Test-Re-test method to find the reliability of the scale on life satisfaction among higher secondary school teachers and the value of reliability was 0.92.

Objectives:

- ✓ To study the level of life satisfaction of higher secondary school teachers.
- ✓ To find out significant difference between female and male higher secondary school teachers with respect to life satisfaction.
- ✓ To find out significant difference between rural and urban higher secondary school teachers with respect to life satisfaction.
- ✓ To find out significant difference between type of management of higher secondary school teachers with respect to life satisfaction.
- ✓ To find out significant difference between medium of instruction of higher secondary school teachers with respect to life satisfaction.
- ✓ To find out significant difference between teaching stream of higher secondary school teachers with respect to life satisfaction.

Hypotheses:

- ✓ The level of life satisfaction of higher secondary school teachers is high.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between female and male higher secondary school teachers with respect to life satisfaction.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between rural and urban higher secondary school teachers with respect to life satisfaction.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between type of management of higher secondary school teachers with respect to life satisfaction.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between medium of instruction of higher secondary school teachers with respect to life satisfaction.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between teaching stream of higher secondary school teachers with respect to life satisfaction.

Data Analysis:

Table 1: Level of Life Satisfaction of Higher Secondary School Teachers

Variables	Sample	N	MEAN	SD	Level
Gender	Male	168	30.99	5.45	Average
	Female	132	30.93	5.74	
Locality of School	Rural	128	31.00	5.53	Average
	Urban	172	30.93	5.35	
Type of Management	Government	110	30.72	5.92	Average
	Govt Aided	114	30.53	5.36	
	Private	78	31.51	5.56	
Medium of Instruction	Tamil	118	30.94	5.66	Average
	English	127	31.26	5.70	
	Both	57	30.33	5.13	
Teaching Stream	Science	135	30.53	5.68	Average
	Maths	106	30.82	5.32	
	Arts	59	31.52	5.31	
Entire Sample		300	30.95	5.57	Average

In this study, based on normal curve of higher secondary school teachers secured scores in between 25.38 to 36.52 (-1σ to +1σ) are classified as average life satisfaction. In the table 1, it was clear that the mean

and standard deviation values. The calculated mean values are less than 36.52 and more than 25.38. Therefore, it is found that the higher secondary school teachers irrespective of their gender, locality of school, type of management, medium of instruction, teaching stream, teaching experience in years, school environment and marital status have average level of life satisfaction.

Table 2: Mean, S.D and “t” Values of Male and Female Towards Life Satisfaction

Gender	N	Mean	SD	“t” Value	Significant at 0.05 level
Male	168	30.99	5.45	0.606	Not Significant
Female	132	30.93	5.74		

In order to find out the significant mean difference between male and female higher secondary school teachers in their life satisfaction score, the investigator calculated ‘t’ value. It is given in the Table 2, it is found to be 0.606, which is not significant at 0.05 levels. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted. It is inferred that male and female higher secondary school teachers do not differ significantly in their life satisfaction.

Table 3: Mean, S.D and “t” Values of Rural and Urban Towards Life Satisfaction

Gender	N	Mean	SD	“t” Value	Significant at 0.05 level
Rural	128	31.00	5.83	0.264	Not Significant
Urban	172	30.93	5.38		

In order to find out the significant mean difference between rural and urban higher secondary school teachers in their life satisfaction score, the investigator calculated ‘t’ value. It is given in the Table 3, it is found to be 0.264, which is not significant at 0.05 levels. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted. It is inferred that rural and urban higher secondary school teachers do not differ significantly in their life satisfaction.

Table 4: “F” Values of Scores of Type of Management Life Satisfaction towards Higher Secondary School Teachers

Group	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	‘F’ Value	LS
Between Groups	31.028	2	15.514	0.498	NS
Within Groups	9254.638	297	31.160		
Total	9285.667	299			

In order to find out the significant mean difference among government, government aided and private type of management of higher secondary school teachers in their life satisfaction score, the investigator calculated ‘F’ value. It is given in the Table 4, it is found to be 0.498, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted. It is inferred that government, govt aided and private type of management higher secondary school teachers do not differ significantly in their life satisfaction.

Table 5: “F” Values of Life Satisfaction Scores of Medium of Instruction towards Higher Secondary School Teachers

Group	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	‘F’ Value	LS
Between Groups	34.413	2	17.206	0.552	NS
Within Groups	9251.254	297	31.149		
Total	9285.667	299			

In order to find out the significant mean difference among Tamil, English and both of medium of instruction of higher secondary school teachers in their life satisfaction score, the investigator calculated ‘F’ value. It is given in the Table 5, it is found to be 0.552, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted. It is inferred that Tamil, English and both medium of instruction of higher secondary school teachers do not differ significantly in their life satisfaction.

Table 6: “F” Values of Life Satisfaction Scores of Teaching Stream towards Higher Secondary School Teachers

Group	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	‘F’ Value	LS
Between Groups	22.946	2	11.473	0.366	NS
Within Groups	9262.721	297	31.188		
Total	9285.667	299			

In order to find out the significant mean difference among and science, maths and arts of teaching stream of higher secondary school teachers in their life satisfaction score, the investigator calculated ‘F’ value. It is given in the Table 6, it is found to be 0.366, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted. It is inferred that science, maths and arts of teaching stream of higher secondary school teachers do not differ significantly in their life satisfaction.

Major Findings of the Study:

- ✓ The study revealed that the higher secondary school teachers with regard to their entire sample, gender, locality of school, type of management, medium of instruction and teaching stream have average level of life satisfaction.
- ✓ The study revealed that there was no significant difference between female and male higher secondary school teachers with regard to their life satisfaction.

- ✓ The study revealed that there was no significant difference between rural and urban higher secondary school teachers with regard to their life satisfaction.
- ✓ The study revealed that there was no significant difference between type of management of higher secondary school teachers with regard to their life satisfaction.
- ✓ The study revealed that there was no significant difference between medium of instruction of higher secondary school teachers with regard to their life satisfaction.
- ✓ The study revealed that there was no significant difference between medium teaching stream of higher secondary school teachers with regard to their life satisfaction.

Conclusion:

The present study showed that higher secondary school teachers had average life satisfaction level. Proper pay scale, job security, work environment should be introduced for them. Teaching is a unique profession that leads to betterment of the society, making of good human being and responsible citizens. Teachers have to perform this strenuous duty with utmost care and expertise. Therefore, their personal satisfaction regarding the life and other factors related to it is very important.

Suggestions and Scope of Further Research:

On the basis of this study the investigator forwards some suggestive measures to attain higher life satisfaction among all groups of teachers.. Teachers should be recruited through a proper channel and effective policy. Teacher- student ratio should be in proper shape. Pay scale, working environment, promotional benefits, after service benefits must be upgraded. Part time and contractual teachers should get job security as well as proper pay scale according to their qualification and work load. The same study could be carried out on teachers from different streams, both in school and college level. Comparative studies could be made to find out the life satisfaction level of regular and distance course teachers also.

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